

IoT Based Patient Monitoring

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ABSTRACT

The propose system gives us the development of a Raspberry Pi based system for Wireless heartbeat, temperature monitoring, eye monitoring for coma patient, saline level Detector. That will easily provide real time information available for many users and can send them alert in critical conditions over Internet. In India many patients are dying because of heart attacks and reason behind this factor is that they are not getting proper help during the period. To give them timely and proper help first want to continuous monitoring of patient health. The fixed monitoring system can be used only when the patient is lying on bed and these systems are huge and only available in the hospitals in ICU. The system is developed for home use by patients that are not in a critical condition but need to be timely monitored by doctor or family. In any critical condition the Mail is send to the doctor or any family member. So that it easily save many lives by providing them quick service.

Keywords: *Raspberry Pi3, IR sensor, Temperature sensor, Motor, Heart beat sensor*

I. INTRODUCTION

Information and communications technologies are transforming our social interactions, over lifestyle and workplaces. One of the most promising applications of information technology is health care & wellness management. Health care is moving from reactive responses to acute conditions to a proactive approach characterized by early detection, prevention and long-term healthcare management. In this framework, health condition monitoring and wellness managements are seen as significant contributors to

individual healthcare and wellbeing. This is particularly important in developed countries with a significant aging population, where information Technology can be employed to significantly improve the management of chronic conditions and, thereby, overall quality of life.

Continuous or even occasional recording of biomedical signals is particularly critical for the diagnosis and treatment of cardiovascular diseases. For example, continuous recording of a heartbeat, temperature and IR sensor by a wearable sensor provides a realistic view of a patient's heart condition by tracking such factors as stress, anxiety, and Depression, during normal daily routines. In the world, Health monitoring system is used in number of field like, car, Home care, Hospital etc. health monitoring is also for daily routine checkup that increase health of people, in this propose system to check the heartbeat, eye blinking, temperature and saline level. Heart bit 140-170bpm for 25 year old person and range between 115- 140 for 60 year old person. That propose system use sensor to sense the different think like temperature, humidity, IR to sense the coma patient eye Motion, if Patients are in comma condition the if thus recovery after doctor treatment or after some period they blink or open the eye then IR sensor sense.

II. SYSTEM DEVELPOMENT

As shown in the propose system the sensors part that consists of different health sensors like as Heartbeat sensor (INVNT 11), temperature sensor and humidity (DHT11), IR sensor.

Fig 1: Block diagram of the system

That sensors are placed at the patient's body. Sensors sense the patient body parameters like heartbeat, temperature, eye motion. The sensed data from the sensors send to the Raspberry Pi.

1. Temperature sensor measure temperature from patient body.
2. Heart beat sensor detector detect Heart beat from patient.
3. IR sensor to detect coma patient eye movement from patient body.
4. Motor that check saline level.
5. After the output of that sensor given to a Raspberry PI through wire. The Raspberry pi continuously reads input from these 3 sensors.
6. The Raspberry Pi is CPU. Then it sends this data to the cloud by sending this data to a particular URL/IP address or android app.
7. Computer then decrypted the information and store at data base. All the information browed by PHP and HTML and show on web page.
8. This proposed system is very useful since the doctor can monitor patient health parameters just by visiting website or URL.
9. And nowadays many IOT and android apps are also being developed. So now the doctor or family members can monitor or track the patient health through the Android apps.

A. Raspberry Pi3

The Raspberry Pi is CPU. It quad-core 64bit CPU, Wi-Fi and Bluetooth. The Raspberry Pi 3 Model B is the third generation Raspberry Pi. Powerful credit-card sized single board computer can be used for many applications and supersedes the original Raspberry Pi model B+ and Raspberry Pi 2 Model B. The Raspberry Pi 3 model B brings you a more

powerful processor, 10x faster than the first generation Raspberry Pi.

Fig 2: Raspberry Pi3 module

Additionally it adds wireless LAN and Bluetooth connectivity making it the ideal solution for powerful connected designs. The digital signals from the sensor are received at the Raspberry pi. Raspberry pi cannot process analog signal. Raspberry pi does not have in built ADC so that the sensors are used in our project they directly give converted digital signal. Then the output of sensor sent to the Raspberry pi. Raspberry pi send the received signals data to mobile devices or cloud through Email or through app or cloud. It is a small, powerful, cheap, hack able and education-oriented computer board introduced in 2012.

B. Heart beat Sensor (NVNT 11)

The sensor gives the digital output of heart beat when a finger is placed on it. When the sensor starts, the LED ashes in union with beat

Fig 3: Heart Beat Sensor

The output generated is in Beats per Minute (BPM) rate. Heart rate data can be really useful whether you are designing an exercise routine, studying your activity or anxiety levels or just want your shirt to blink with your heart beat. The problem is that heart rate can be difficult to measure.

C. Temperature Sensor (DTH 11)

It is a sensor used to measure temperature and humidity. The DHT11 series are precision integrated circuit temperature and humidity sensors, whose output voltage linearly proportional to the Celsius (Centigrade) temperature.

Fig 4: Temperature Sensor

It measures temperature more accurately than thermistor. It is sealed and does not undergo oxidation. It does not require output voltage to be amplified.

D. IR Sensor

The IR Sensor- Single is a general purpose proximity sensor. It use for collision detection. The module consists of a IR emitter and IR receiver pair. The high precision IR receiver always detects IR signal. The module consists of 358comparator IC. The output of sensor is high whenever it IR frequency and low otherwise. The on-board LED indicator helps user to check status of the sensor without using any additional hardware. The power consumption of this module is low. It gives a digital output.

Fig 5: IR Sensor

An infrared sensor is an electronic device that emits in order to sense some aspects of the surroundings. An IR sensor can measure the heat of an object as well as detects the motion. The types of sensors measures only infrared radiation, rather than emitting it is called as a passive IR sensor. That types of radiations are invisible to our eyes that can be detected by an

infrared sensor. The emitter is simply an IR LED (Light Emitting Diode) and the detector is simply an IR photo diode which is sensitive to IR light of the same wavelength as that emitted by the IR LED. When IR light falls on the photo diode the resistances and these output voltages, change in proportion to the magnitude of the IR light received.

III. RESULTS

Our project shows the location of patient with the help of google maps, which is shown below

Fig 6: Location tracer of patient

Our system also shows certain parameters of patient (Temperature, IR, Heart beat) and the surrounding of patient (Humidity) which are shown below:

Fig 7: Patient's temperature

Fig 8: Humidity around the patient

Fig 9: IR of patient

Fig 10. Patient's heart beats

IV. ADVANTAGES,

APPLICATIONS&FUTURE SCOPE

A. Advantages.

- IOT monitoring very helpful when need to monitor, maintain record and keep track of changes in the health parameters of the patient over the period of time. So with the IOT health monitoring the health parameters database changes. Doctors can take the reference of these changes or the history of the patient while suggesting the treatment or the medicines to the patient.
- Hospital stays are minimized due to remote patient monitoring.
- Hospital visits for normal routine checkups are minimized.
- Patient health parameter data is stored over the cloud. So it is more beneficial than maintaining the records on printed papers kept in the less or even the digital records which are kept in a particular computer, laptop or memory device like pen drive. Because there are chances that

these devices can get corrupt and data might be lost. Whereas, in case of IOT, the cloud storage is more reliable and does have minimal chances of data loss.

B. Applications

- This system is more useful in Hospital ICU and in ambulance.
- IOT healthcare is the most demanding Field in the medical area. For the senior citizen living alone or living with 1 or 2 members. The proposed system really helpful when family members need to go out for some emergency work.
- Disable patients can use this project. Disable patients who find it really difficult to go to doctors on daily basis or for those patients who need continuous monitoring from the doctor.

C. Future Scope

- For Coma patient add more sensors to check the coma patient health status. Sensors like motion sensor.
- In future Using Wireless sensor to minimize connection.
- UDO board replace raspberry pi. Because has more features.
- Using different type of sensor, it is possible to check the patient status.
- Use for Handicap and old age patient.

V. CONCLUSION.

The proposed system uses sensor technology as an emerging element for healthcare services. The proposed system a computer and mobile monitoring system is presented, which is able to continuously monitor the patient's heart beat, temperature and humidity, coma patient eye motion and other critical parameters of patients. The system is able to carry out a long term monitoring of patients condition and equipped with an emergency rescue mechanism. This system is also beneficial for physically handicapped and Disable patients who find it really difficult to go to the Hospital on daily basis and patients who need continuous monitoring from the doctor. In the highly developing area, where directly or indirectly, everything is dependent on computation and information technology, Raspberry Pi to be a smart,

economic and efficient platform for implementing the health monitoring system. The Raspberry pi is a single computer board with credit card size that can be used for many tasks that your computer does. Comparison with other board Raspberry pi is more advanced in terms of cost, speed, complexity etc. The proposed system, switch to wireless technology to have a better estimation of health monitoring system.

REFERENCES

1. Megha Koshti and Prof. Dr. Sanjay Ganorkar, "IOT Based Health Monitoring System by Using Raspberry Pi and ECG Signal", International Journal of Innovative Research in Science, Engineering and Technology, ISO 3297: 2007 Certified Organization, Vol. 5, Issue: 5, May, 2016, pp.8977-8985.
2. Chetan T. Kasundra and Prof. A. S. Shirsat, "Raspberry -Pi Based Health Monitoring System", International Journal of Advanced Research in Electrical, Electronics and Instrumentation Engineering, Vol. 4, Issue: 8, August, 2015, pp.7147-7154.
3. Prashant Patil, Rohan Waichal, et al., "Patient Health Monitoring System using IOT", International Research Journal of Engineering and Technology (IRJET), Vol. 4, Issue: 01, Jan, 2017, pp.638-641.
4. Shivam Gupta, Shivam Kashaudhan, et al., "IOT based Patient Health Monitoring System", International Research Journal of Engineering and Technology (IRJET), Vol. 4, Issue: 03, Mar, 2017, pp.2316-2319.
5. Ruhani Rahman, NurShima Abdul Aziz, et al. "IOT based Personal Health Care Monitoring Device for Diabetic Patients", IEEE, 2017, pp.168- 173.
6. Ovidiu Apostu, Bogdan Hagi, Sever Paşca, "Wireless ECG Monitoring and Alarm System Using ZigBee" 2011 the International Symposium on ADVANCED TOPIC IN ELECTRICAL ENGINEERING 2068 - 7966/ATEE 2011.
7. Warsuzarina Mat Jubadi, Siti Farid atul Aisyah Mohdahak", "Heartbeat Monitoring Alert via SMS", 978-1-4244-4683-4/09/\$25.00 ©2009 IEEE.
8. Goutam Motika, Abinash Prusty," Wireless Fetal Heartbeat Monitoring System Using Zig Bee & IEEE 802.15.4 Standard", 2011 Second International Conference on Emerging Applications of Information Technology, 978-0-7695- 4329-1/11 \$26.00 © 2011 IEEE DOI 10.1109/EAIT.2011.89
9. S. M. Mahalle, P. V. Ingole, "Design and Implementation of Wireless Body Area Sensor Network Based Health Monitoring System", International Journal of Engineering Research & Technology, Vol. 2 Issue 6, pp. 105-113, June 2013.
10. "Healthcare Monitoring System Using Wireless Sensor Network", D. Mahesh Kumar, Department of Electronics, PSG College of Arts and Science, Coimbatore - 641 014. Volume 04, Issue 01 Pages:1497-1500 (2012), ISSN: 0975-0290